

MODELLING THE IMPACT OF COAL SEAM METHANE ON THE MONGOLIAN ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT. Energy independence is one of the most important issues for almost every country and the world. Mongolia strives to have various types of energy sources and reduce energy dependence. Energy dependence always influences economic dependence of any country. Utilising its own country's resources is optimal to reduce energy dependence. In recent years, the Mongolian Government has been encouraging unconventional oil and gas exploration and foreign investment and implementing supporting policies, such as coal bed (seam) methane. As a result of these activities, unconventional oil and gas investment and exploration have been intensified in the last few years in Mongolia, especially during pandemics. There are 32 oil and gas blocks in Mongolia and coal bed methane exploration and foreign investments have been invested in eight blocks. In 2022, some foreign investment companies are going to introduce proven reserves of coal bed methane to the Mongolian Government and Parliament. Therefore, we have to model the positive and negative impacts of coal bed methane on the Mongolian economy and find methods to increase the positive sides. Unfortunately, there is no experience in any situation for unconventional oil and gas exploration, extraction, and field development. Because of it, we have cooperated with Australian scientists and experts and completed some studies for making a model of the impact of coal seam methane on the Mongolian economy. For today's condition, the Mongolian Government or Mongolian private companies can't process coal bed methane activities because of lack of capital expenses and experience. To raise the positive impacts of coal bed methane, foreign investment is of course very important. There are some main purposes to model the impact of coal seam methane on the Mongolian economy.

Key words: cost, price, payment, profit, tax.

Introduction

Team of experts considered the data that had been received from operators, and based on this, scoped out three representative asset scenarios for coal bed methane (CBM) business operating in Mongolia. The main purpose of defining three distinct asset scenarios / cases was to provide a sufficiently broad range of projects, in terms of development scale, scope and cost, to represent the potential range of CBM business opportunity in Mongolia. This is relevant from an investor perspective contemplating new business entry into Mongolia and also highly relevant to Mongolian authorities who wish to design their fiscal regime so that it meets a range of needs, some of which are essential and some desirable, depending on the strategic goals of the State, including:

- Attracting sufficient investment and skill sets into the country, if not locally available, not just for the short-term but also for longer-term mutual benefit;
- Promoting economic growth and local employment from construction, infrastructure development and operations;
- Increasing energy independence and energy reliability within Mongolia (Gantumur, 2019); and
- Unlocking stranded resources that can be used domestically, and if sufficient surplus exists, exporting and selling internationally to generate revenue for the State, support the Federal budget and the balance of trade.

Three CBM development scenarios, comprising a Low, Mid and a High Case, were considered to be sufficiently broad to assess and compare fiscal regimes, without being too onerous in terms of the volume of input and output data to be analysed. After consideration of data received from operators the three scenarios or cases were broadly defined as following:

- Low Case: Small scale CBM to liquefied natural gas (LNG) production for transportation fuel to the local market, e.g. as fuel for cars, trains and trucks. This scenario assumed 30-32 Billion standard cubic feet (Bscf) of gas sales from an

initial undeveloped resource of about 40 Bscf. Development costs (CAPEX) were assumed to be about \$USD 51 million and Exploration and Appraisal (E&A) capital of about \$USD 5 million.

- Mid Case: CBM for gas fired power generation for local market base load power at 80 Mega Watts (MW). This scenario assumed about 146 Bscf of sales gas from an initial undeveloped resource of about 188 Bscf. Development costs were assumed to be about \$USD 236 million and E&A capital of about \$USD 11 million.

- High Case: CBM for pipeline export to an international buyer. This scenario assumed about 1.015 trillions of standard cubic feet of gas (Tscf) of sales gas from an initial undeveloped resource of about 1.48 Tscf. Development costs were assumed to be about \$USD 1,856 million and E&A capital of about \$USD 44 million.

The discount date is set to 1 January 2021 after the completion of exploration and appraisal programme and at the time when project participants decide whether the investment in project is attractive to progress into development phase. Therefore, negative cash flows from exploration and appraisal costs paid by contractors are sunk and excluded from the net cash flows and net present value calculation. The impact from sunk cost income tax deductible for tax royalty regime and cost recoverable for product sharing contract (PSC) regime is included in the cash flows and net present value calculation. With all three cases the development takes place after the E&A phase sufficiently defines and de-risks the resources, leading to first gas operations around 2024 for the Low and Mid Cases. However, for the High Case, where gas will be exported to international buyers through a pipeline, the first production is estimated to be around 2028 as the project will need finalisation of gas sales and gas transportation agreements to end users via an onshore pipeline constructed and owned by a third party. As with all CBM developments, unlike conventional,

the field appraisal and development continue throughout the operational phase until late field life to maintain plateau production by compensating for the more rapid decline rates and wider geographical footprints typically observed with CBM. All three cases assumed about 22% volume reduction from the initial resource as a result of field fuel usage, CO₂ removal, gas shrinkage and other operational related losses. The upstream development scope in all three cases excluded gas processing plant and capital as it was assumed, based on the local market setting, that the gas processing would be handled under a tolling arrangement with a third party. This cost is, therefore, included as part of the field operating expenses (OPEX) assumption. Likewise, the water treatment costs, that are also a typical CBM feature, are handled as an OPEX via a tolling arrangement through a third party plant. In all cases the CBM development scope and costs were limited to the upstream project only. In other words, the fiscal point of sale for the gas would be the field export pipeline flange to one of three potential market entry points. From a fiscal modelling viewpoint, it is very important to be clear about the point of sale, where the gas produced is valued, as that location defines the upstream development scope and costs that are recoverable (for PSCs) or depreciable (for Royalty-Tax Regimes) and the scope and costs that fall outside the petroleum fiscal framework. For the purposes of this exercise and for simplicity the modelling scope encompasses upstream assets to the point of sale as defined below.

1. Low Case: Point of sale would be from the field exit flange / at the inlet flange of the feed line into the small-scale LNG plant.

2. Mid Case: Point of sale would be from the field exit flange / at the inlet flange of the feed line into the power station.

3. High Case: Point of sale would be from the field gas compression and treatment plant exit flange / at the inlet flange to the pipeline connection point.

Methodology

Model inputs estimated capital and operating expenditures for Low Case, Mid Case and High Case were provided by current Operators in Mongolia CBM projects. The Energy team reviewed these cost estimates and made necessary adjustments to normalise the data based on benchmarked information and in some cases to anonymise the data from their sources. All the cost estimates were provided in 2020 real values and then inflated using 2% inflation per annum assumption to the time they were incurred. The basis and the unit cost assumptions for capital and operating expenditures are described in Table 1.

Estimated gas price assumptions were provided by CBM Operators in Mongolia, and like the cost information this was adjusted to normalise prices based on a range of market price ranges provided for each case and anonymise the Operator information. All price estimates were assumed to be 2020 real values and then inflated using 2% inflation per annum assumption. The assumed domestic gas prices and export gas price assumptions are described in Table 2 and are reported as prices per million British thermal units (MMBtu) that converts gas volumes to units of heat.

No analysis has been performed on the gas market or gas market risks as part of this study. The following gas market sectors have been identified (Zoljargal, 2018):

Table 1. Cost assumptions for capital and operating expenditures

CAPEX and OPEX Assumptions	Basis ad Unit Costs
Well and Facility CAPEX	\$USD 0.450 MM / well
Gas Production related OPEX (variable)	\$USD 0.050 / Mscf raw gas
Water Treatment OPEX (variable)	\$USD 0.100 /barrel of water
Workover, Maintenance & Field Operation OPEX	\$USD 0.05 MM fixed per year and \$USD 150000 per online well
Gas Processing Tariffs (OPEX)	\$USD 0.750 / Mscf raw gas
Abandonment Cost	6.5 % of well and facility CAPEX to be spent equally 5 years after the drilling campaign
Exploration and Appraisal	10 % of CAPEX for Low Case 5 % of CAPEX for Mid Case 2.5 % of CAPEX for High Case

Table 2. Gas price assumptions

Market	Netback Gas Price
Domestic Gas Sales for Low Case and Mid Case	\$USD 5.50 / MMBtu
Export Gas Sales for High Case	

- Urban Gas Demand. This market comprises supply for residential use for winter heating and gas vehicles. The winter heating demand occurs from October to May, whereas gas demand for gas vehicles would be classified as regular use.

- Industrial Gas Demand. This market comprises industrial and chemical enterprises. The number of users will increase as the economy develops.

- Heat and Power Cogeneration. Currently, all heat and power cogeneration plants in Mongolia are coal fired.

The substitution of coal for gas is possible subject to available and reliable gas supply in sufficient quantities. In addition to the above, there is the potential to supply gas to international markets such as China. Significant gas resources would be required to supply such a market and justify capital investment in facilities and pipelines. For the Low Case, an ex-field delivery price of \$USD 5.50 / MMBtu was assumed. With estimated LNG processing and liquefaction fees of \$USD 3.0 - 3.5 /MMBtu for LNG (Adam and Garnett, 2021), an assumed distribution fee of \$USD 0.75-1.00/MMBtu (Adam and Garnett, 2021), LNG would be sold to end users at a market price slightly below \$USD 10 /MMBtu. At this price level, LNG was considered to be competitive to liquid fuel alternatives, i.e. sufficiently cheaper than petrol for cars or diesel for trucks / trains to incentivise the switch to LNG. For the Mid Case, an ex-field delivery of \$USD 5.50 / MMBtu was assumed for gas sold to a power generation plant. At this price level, gas would be competitive to diesel, fuel oil, or even coal if environmental impacts are taken into consideration. For the High Case, an ex-field delivery price of \$USD 7.50 /MMBtu was assumed

based on an estimated landed gas price in international markets of about \$USD 8.50 / MMBtu with \$USD 1.00 / Mscf for pipeline transportation fee (Busby et al., 2011). Additional price and cost sensitivities were not conducted for the scope and purposes of this exercise.

The input summaries for each of these cases are presented in Table 3 to Table 5 (Janarbaatar, 2018).

Low Case: Small Scale CBM to LNG Production for Transportation Fuel to the Local Market.

Mid Case: CBM for Gas Fired Power Generation for Local Market Base Load Power at 80 MW

High Case: CBM for Pipeline Export to an International Buyer.

Table 3. Development input summary for low case

Development Metrics	Value	Unit
Raw Gas Production	40.6	Bscf
Total Sales Gas Produced	31.5	Bscf
Total Water Produced	19.2	MMstb
Development Wells Drilled	106	#Wells
Average Recovery Per Well (post fuel+flare use)	0.30	Bscf/Well

Table 4. Development input summary for mid case

Development Metrics	Value	Unit
Raw Gas Production	188.2	Bscf
Total Sales Gas Produced	146.1	Bscf
Total Water Produced	89.1	MMstb
Development Wells Drilled	492	#Wells
Average Recovery Per Well (post fuel+flare use)	0.30	Bscf/Well

Table 5. Development input summary for high case

Development Metrics	Value	Unit
Raw Gas Production	1477.6	Bscf
Total Sales Gas Produced	1147.0	Bscf
Total Water Produced	700.2	MMstb
Development Wells Drilled	3872	#Wells
Average Recovery Per Well (post fuel+flare use)	0.30	Bscf/Well

Mongolia CBM projects currently operate under Production Sharing Contracts (PSC) with cost recovery and profit split between Government and Contractors (Otto et al, 2006). The revision of Mongolia Petroleum Law in 2014 simplifies certain fiscal terms including the elimination of income tax, dividend withholding tax, and value added tax and customs tariff. Key Government take fiscal terms for CBM projects are negotiable with the authorities for each individual Operator and potentially for each individual license. In accordance with the 2014 Petroleum Law, royalty ranges from 5 % to 10 % of gross revenues. The cost recovery limit and profit sharing for the Government are negotiable on project-by-project basis. The profit sharing for Government is not graduated but applied on a production rate threshold. For the analysis, royalty rate is assumed to be 7.5 % as the midpoint of the 5-10 % range (Dugerjav, 2018). The Energy team has reviewed the cost recovery limit and profit sharing for Government assumptions made by Operators and made necessary adjustments to

normalise and anonymise the fiscal terms (Janarbaatar, 2018). Signature bonus and production bonuses are not included in the analysis. Table 6 summarises the fiscal terms assumptions (Gen, 2018).

Table 6. Summary of Mongolian PSC terms (Binderman, 1999; Smith, 2013)

Fiscal terms	Petroleum Law	Assumptions in the analysis
Royalty	5 % - 10 %	7.5 %
Cost Recovery Limit	For CBM - to be determined	70 %
Profit Sharing for Government		
0-1 Million m ³ /day		30.0 %
1 – 2 Million m ³ /day		32.5 %
2 – 3 Million m ³ /day		35.0 %
3– 4 Million m ³ /day		37.5 %
>4 Million m ³ /day		40.0 %
Tax Rate [2]	Exempted	0.0 %
Dividend Withholding Tax	Exempted	0.0 %
VAT ad Customs Tariff	Exempted	0.0 %
Contractor Participating Interest	100 %	100 %
Signature Bonus	As proposed by Contractor	Not included
Production Bonus	As proposed by Contractor	Not included

Model Inputs for Low, Mid and High Cases (Adam and Garnett, 2021) are presented in figures from 1 to 6.

Conclusion

In all cases, the Royalty-Tax regime yields significantly higher undiscounted cashflows and rates of return to investors, compared to the PSC regime.

- Conversely, in all cases Government cashflow and discounted cashflow are higher for all cases under the PSC regime. However, when Government take is too high it does not encourage new investments, few or no projects will be developed resulting in sub-optimal Government take. The fiscal regime should be designed to encourage new investments which will result in multiple project developments and optimised Government cashflow at an aggregate level.

- From an Investor / Operator / Contractor perspective, projects exemplified by the Low Case could not be supported under the PSC and yielded only marginally economic results under the Royalty-Tax terms (Figure 1, Figure 2). The impact of this is that under the PSC regime there will be less gas supply that can be developed compared to a Royalty-Tax regime. Natural resource opportunities tend to follow distributions where there are far more “low case” opportunities than “high case” ones. The fiscal model chosen influences how many opportunities are economic. Ultimately, lower supply will tend to cause higher gas prices and, thus, fewer opportunities for economic development.

- Similarly, marginal projects under a PSC framework, as demonstrated by the Mid Case would struggle to pass through the internal decision-making process for most companies unless returns could be supported by further technical improvement and/or commercial improvement and/or some type of fiscal incentive (Figure 3, Figure 4). The Mid Case project yielded economic results under the Royalty-Tax regime terms and could proceed under this fiscal regime.

- Projects like the High Case could proceed on the economic merits, but the reality is that investment decisions are not made on economic merits alone (Figure 5, Figure 6). For most successful businesses, a range of decision criteria are used for their investment decisions. Decisions of this scale, or requiring entry into a new country, would normally be supported by a comprehensive risk and opportunity

assessment that is both quantitative and qualitative in nature, i.e. would include a range of non-technical risks.

- Compared to the PSC regime, the Royalty-Tax regime treats smaller scale, lower value projects less harshly than larger scale, more profitable projects. At the same time, the Royalty-Tax regime still provides a “good” level of return to the Investor / Operator / Contractor for those large-scale, more profitable cases.

- For the larger scale projects exemplified by the High Case, the returns are high under both regimes, with better after-Tax returns for the Operator under the Royalty-Tax regime at all discount rates considered. The high returns for such a large-scale venture would be considered commensurate with the higher capital exposures (i.e. larger amounts of capital placed at-risk) involved, the longer lead

Fig. 1. Upstream Development Capital – Low Case

Fig. 2. Upstream Operating

Fig. 3. Upstream Development Capital – Mid Case

Fig. 4. Upstream Operating Costs – Mid Case

timings to first production, the commercial complexity of the project and higher risks in a new resource play in a new business environment.

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References

Binderman K., 1999. Production-Sharing Agreements; An Economic Analysis. Oxford Institute for Energy Studies.

WPM 25. October 1999.

Busby C., Dachis B., Dahlby B., Rethinking Rates: Why There is a Better Way to Tax Oil and Gas Development. № 333. Sept 2011. C. D. Howe Institute Commentary. Fiscal and Tax Competitiveness.

Comparative assessment of fiscal regimes. Mongolian coal bed methane, ed. S. Adam, A. Garnett, Australia – Mongolia Extractives Programme (AMEP) 2021. Ulaanbaatar.

Dugerjav L., 2018. Summarising study in the Energy Sector, Proceeding of International Conference on Oil and Gas Conference, 19, Part 1, 213-229.

Fig. 5. Upstream Development Capital – High Case

Fig. 6. Upstream Operating Costs – High Case

Gantumur S., 2019. The geothermal energy study in Arkhangai province, Proceeding of International Conference on Oil and Gas Conference, 19, Part 1, 179-186.

Gen E., ed. 2018. Updating Energy Sector Development Plan. Technical Assistance Consultant's Report, Asian Development Bank, Ulaanbaatar.

Janarbaatar J., 2018. Report on Energy sector of Mongolia, The Ministry of Energy, Ulaanbaatar.

Smith J. L., 2013. Issues in extractive resource taxation: A review of research methods and models, Resources Policy, 38, 320-331.

Otto L., Andrews C., Cawood F., Doggett M., Guj P., Stermole., Titon J., 2006. Mining Royalties: A Global Study of Their Impact on Investors, Government, and Civil Society. Directions in Development Energy and Mining.

2006. The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development / World Bank.

Zoljargal J., 2018. Possibility and Development in Energy Sector of Mongolia - Natural gas and Crude oil. Ulaanbaata